

Engage.O Framework Assessment Questionnaire - New Members

This questionnaire aims to collect information about the experience of new employees onboarding with the Engage.O framework.

* Indicates required question

1. You are being invited to participate in the research project: About the Engage.O *
framework, a framework used to onboarding members of time A, whose responsible researcher is Anonymous. The objectives of the project are: Verify the application of the Engage.O framework at the moment A. You are being invited because you have been onboarding into the Engage.O framework. Mr. You have full freedom to refuse to participate or cancel your consent, at any stage of the research, without any penalty for the treatment you receive in this service at Instituto Anonimo. If you agree to participate, your participation consists of an interview and filling out a form about the team's Onboarding process. Both will be accompanied by the person responsible for the research. All research with human beings involves risks to participants. In this research, as it is an interview there is no risk. The following benefits are also expected from this research: pointing out the positive points of having an onboarding process, validating the Engage.O framework. If you deem it necessary, you will have time to reflect on your participation, consulting, if necessary, your family or other people who can help you make a free and informed decision. (Res. 466/2012-CNS, IV.I.c)

Mark only one oval.

Agree

Disagree

2. We guarantee that you will maintain the confidentiality and privacy of your participation and data during all phases of the research and subsequently in scientific dissemination (Item IV.3.e, of CNS Resolution No. 466 of 2012). You can contact the responsible researcher Anonimo at any time for additional information *

Mark only one oval.

- Agree
- Disagree

3. How long have you worked with software team? *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 1 year
- Less than 2 year
- Less than 3 year
- Less than 4 year
- Less than 5 year
- More than 5 year

4. This scale consists of a number of words that represent different feelings and emotions. Read each item and indicate to what extent you felt this way, in the first week on team A when you were starting your Onboarding process *

Mark only one oval per row.

	extremely	quite a bit extremely	moderately	a little	very slightly or not at all
Upset	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Strong	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Scared	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Proud	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Nervous	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Irritable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Interested	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Inspired	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Hostile	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Guilty	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Excited	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Enthusiastic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Distressed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Determined	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Attentive	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ashamed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Anxious	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Alert	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Afraid	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Active	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

5. Have you had previous experiences in companies without an onboarding process? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

6. What was positive about this experience? *

7. What was negative about this experience? *

8. Do you consider the Engage.O framework effective in the onboarding process for new employees? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

9. What do you consider positive about the Onboarding Engage.O process? *

10. What do you consider negative about the Onboarding Engage.O process? * *

11. What is the difference between the Engage.O Onboarding process and the Onboarding process of your previous company/team? *

12. Complete the sentence: "In "Phase 1: Immersion" I participated in five activities: Presentation of the team, Presentation of the environment, Self-presentation (personal Map), Preparation of the environment and Presentation of organizational rules. When carrying out these tasks I felt.....

..... .."

13. Complete the sentence: ""Phase 2: Elucidating Expectations" has three activities: Essential Technology Training, Project Presentation and Project Rules and Good Practices. Understanding the expectations of what is expected of my work made me feel..... ""

14. Complete a sentence: ""Phase 3: Tools and Processes" has two activities: Presentation of Processes and Presentation of Tools. I consider this phase"

15. Complete a sentence: ""Phase 4: Practical Activities" has two activities: Assisted Execution and Ramp-Up. This phase was"

16. Complete the sentence: "I consider the activity: "Assisted Execution Activities""

17. This scale consists of a number of words that represent different feelings and emotions. Read each item and indicate to what extent you felt this way, after completing your onboarding process on team A *

Mark only one oval per row.

	extremely	quite a bit extremely	moderately	a little	very slightly or not at all
Upset	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Strong	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Scared	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Proud	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Nervous	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Irritable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Interested	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Inspired	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Hostile	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Guilty	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Excited	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Enthusiastic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
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Afraid	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Active	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

18. *Mark only one oval.*

Option 1

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